

Results and Discussion

The reactions of boric acid with various monobasic bidentate chelating ligands in refluxing acetic anhydride give chelates of borooacetate of the type (L-L) B(CH₃COO)₂ (Fig. 1). Elemental analyses support their formulations. These complexes easily hydrolysed in contact with water giving rise to CH₃COOH, B(OH)₃ and the corresponding chelating ligands.

Infrared spectra of some of these chelates have been measured. Two strong bands observed at 1710 cm⁻¹ and 1268 cm⁻¹ in (I) may be assigned as C=O and C-O of acetate group. On the other hand, chelated C...O (sym) observed at 1598 cm⁻¹. Overlapping bands of C...O and B-O (asym) appeared at 1375 cm⁻¹, while B-O (sym) observed at 1060 cm⁻¹. The assignments are based mainly on those for comparable boron and beryllium chelates⁶⁻⁸, and the spectra of free acetylacetone and its metal complexes. The bands are generally broadened by chelating, and interpretation is made difficult by close overlap in several regions. The two closely spaced bands between 1490 and 1600 cm⁻¹ have caused confusion.⁷⁻¹¹ Thus, our band assignments should be taken as purely tentative, because the vibrations must be extensively coupled. A strong band observed at 1535 cm⁻¹ in the complex (hap) B(CH₃COO)₂ (III) may be considered as chelated νC=O (which appears at 1635 cm⁻¹ in the free "hap-H"). This, along with the absence of any OH bands, suggest chelated nature of orthohydroxyacetophenone in this complex. Analogously, it has been presumed that salicylaldehyde and acetoacetonilide act as chelating ligands in the complexes (sal)B(CH₃COO)₂ (II) and (aact)B(CH₃COO)₂ (IV) respectively.

The most intense u. v. bands for the chelates I-III are given in experimental section. Weaker bands have also been observed for II and III in the region 245-290 nm, which is characteristic of the benzene ring and (possibly) are associated with vibrational effects on the π→π* transitions. The former bands correspond very closely to the strongest bands observed for boron difluoride complexes¹⁰ and may be attributed to charge-transfer transitions in the delocalized π electron systems of the chelating ligands.

In all the four chelates isolated, boron atom may be in a near tetrahedral environment by four oxygen donor atoms (Fig. 1). This is in the line with the recent crystal structure determination of the benzoyl-acetonate-BF₂ compound¹² (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1

Fig. 2.

In this connection one should mention the work of Heimann and Sagredon,¹³ who recently reported the syntheses of α- and γ-pyrones by the heat treatment of borocarboxylates of various enolisable β-diketones.

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Addition of Alcohols to Substituted Dicyandiamides

R. L. DUTTA* & AKOIJAM MANIHAR SINGH**

Inorganic Chemistry Laboratory, The University of Burdwan, Burdwan-713101

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THE inaugural report of Dutta and Rây¹ on the addition of alcohols to dicyandiamide in the presence of cupric salts has generated a good deal of interest²⁻⁶. We describe herein some preliminary results of similar studies with phenyldicyandiamide (and some other substituted dicyandiamides).

Phenyldicyandiamide (2 mols.) reacts with alcohols in the presence of cupric salts (1 mol.) to give violet crystals of bis (1-phenylamidino-o-alkylurea) copper(II) salts. Reaction of 1 mol. phenyldicyandiamide and 1 mol. cupric chloride in presence of an alcohol gives

* Senior author.

** On leave from Imphal College, Imphal, Manipur.

quite readily deep blue to blue green sparingly soluble dichloro mono (1-phenylamidino-*o*-alkylurea) copper(II) in almost quantitative yield. This latter reaction appears to be general and occurs with ease with unsubstituted dicyandiamide as well, which has escaped the attention of Dutta and Rây¹.

Reaction of copper(II) nitrate with phenyldicyandiamide in 1 : 1 ratio in *ethanol* gives a green powder which has been identified as di(nitrato) mono (1-phenylamidino-*o*-ethylurea) copper(II). Copper(II) sulphate (1 mol.) and phenyldicyandiamide (1 mol.) in *methanol* gives green coloured sulphato mono(1-phenylamidino-*o*-methylurea) copper(II). Phenyldicyandiamide has a strong sharp nitrile band at 2222 cm⁻¹ which is completely absent in the alcohol addition products. There is no C=O stretch at 1740 cm⁻¹ indicating that the products are not substituted guanylureas. Instead all the complexes have C-O-R stretch at ~ 1124 cm⁻¹ to support the 1-phenylamidino-*o*-alkylurea structure.

The infrared spectrum of the sulphato complex (1166, 1096, 1000, 958 cm⁻¹) shows evidence of bidentate sulphato group⁷. The bis(ligand) copper(II) nitrate and chloride salts are as expected biunivalent electrolytes in methanol while the dinitrato and the dichloromono (ligand) copper(II) complexes are substantially ionised in methanol, their conductivity increasing with dilution. This indicates that the coordinated nitrate and chloride are being solvolysed. The sulphato- and the nitrato mono(ligand) copper(II) complexes have no parallel yet in the metal biguanide chemistry⁸, and they also constitute the first examples reported in the family of 1-amidino-*o*-alkylurea metal complexes.

⁹ The electronic spectra of bis(1-phenylamidino-*o*-alkylurea) copper(II) salts conform to a square planar [CuN₄] chromophore (λ_{\max} 18 kK in acetonitrile). Compare square planar bis(biguanide) copper(II)⁹ (19.1 kK in water); bis(1-amidino-*o*-alkylurea) copper(II)² (18.5 kK in water), bis(ethylenediamine) copper(II)¹⁰ (18.2 kK in water), tetrakis(benzimidazole) copper(II) perchlorate¹¹ (19.0 kK, solid phase).

Compared to copper(II), nickel(II) is much less efficient in forcing addition of alcohol to phenyldicyandiamide. A reaction of 1 mol. of nickel chloride and two mols. of phenyldicyandiamide takes around 40 hrs to go to completion while that with copper(II) takes 6-8 hrs. (both on steam bath). The nickel(II) complexes are orange yellow, diamagnetic and hence conform to [NiN₄] square planar geometry.

o-Chloro- and *p*-chlorophenyldicyandiamide also give similar reactions.

It is interesting to note that phenyldicyandiamide¹² (m.p. 197°) can be recovered in ~ 95% yield after refluxing in methanol for 40 hr (Found, m.p. 196°; N, 35.3; Calc. N, 35.0 per cent). Phenyldicyandiamide also remains unchanged after 60 hr reflux in ethanol (recovery ~ 95%, m.p. 196°, N, 35.1 per cent).

Details of these studies will be reported in due course.

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Application of Thermographic Analysis in the Studies of Reclaimed Rubber Compounds

KALYAN K. CHAKRABORTY*

Department of Physical Chemistry,
Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science,
Calcutta-700032

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THERMOGRAPHIC analysis has recently been an important analytical tool in the field of polymer chemistry and technology. Differential thermal analysis (DTA) is being used frequently in the investigations of the influence of various factors on the thermogram characteristics of different elastomer systems^{1,2}.

In order to have some definite ideas on the thermal characteristics of reclaimed rubber under different perspectives a modified form of the DTA section of the Derivatograph of Paulik and coworkers³ has been fabricated in our laboratory. The instrument has been calibrated by using pure compounds like benzoic acid and phthalimide by way of checking their T_m values (which are well separated from each other). For comparative studies on heat of reaction, the instrument has been standardised against the known heat of reaction for the dehydration of copper sulphate pentahydrate utilizing its last peak area.

* Present address; Institute of Materials Science University of Connecticut, U.S.A.